

Implementing NRR

An Algorithmic Approach

Outline

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Adjacency Matrix

- An adjacency matrix for a graphical network contains a '1' in position (i,j) if node i is directly linked with node j via an edge (direct connection)
- We want to use the adjacency matrix to study indirect connections.

The diagram shows a grid representing an adjacency matrix. The grid is 5 rows high and 6 columns wide. The top row is labeled 'j' above the second column. The left side is labeled 'i' to the left of the second row. The grid is composed of 30 cells, with the bottom-right cell being significantly larger than the others.

Procedure / Algorithm

- If there is a '0' in (i,j) it means there is no direct connection between nodes i and j

				0	

The diagram shows a 5x6 grid representing a matrix. The top row is labeled 'j' above the fifth column. The left side is labeled 'i' to the left of the fourth row. The cell at the intersection of the fourth row and fifth column contains the value '0'.

Procedure / Algorithm 2 - Backward Search

- Step 1: Consider row i , columns 1 through $j - 1$
- Step 2: If there exists a 1 there, go to Step 3, else go to Step 4'
- Step 3: Note down the column number of the '1.' Say it is column k , where $1 \leq k \leq j$.

i		1		0	

Procedure / Algorithm 3

- Step 4: In column k , consider rows $i-1$ through 1 in descending order (bigger value to smaller value). If there is a 1 encountered there, note its row number. Say it is l .

		1			
		1	0		

The diagram shows a grid representing a matrix. The columns are labeled k and j above the grid. The rows are labeled l and i to the left of the grid. The grid has 6 columns and 5 rows. The cell at row l , column k contains the value 1. The cell at row i , column k contains the value 1, and the cell at row i , column j contains the value 0. All other cells are empty.

Procedure / Algorithm 4

- Step 5: From position (l,k) , scan row l , columns k through j . If position (l,j) is a 1, then stop, since there is an indirect path between i and j . The path is $(i,k) \rightarrow (k,l) \rightarrow (l,j)$. It is a four node path, with three edges.
- Step 6: If no 1 is encountered in Step 4, there is no indirect connection yet found.
- Step 7: If more than one '1' is encountered in Step 4 say on rows l_1, l_2, \dots and Step 5 using the l_1 1 was unsuccessful, repeat Step 5 using the second such '1', namely the one in row l_2 column k .

			k		j	
l			1		1	
i			1		0	

Procedure / Algorithm 5 - Forward Search

- Step 4': Consider row i , columns $j+1$, through n . If there exists a `1' therein, go to Step 5'
- Step 5': Note down its column number. Say it is k' where $j+1 \leq k' \leq n$.
- Step 6': In column k' consider rows $i+1$ through n . If a `1' is encountered, note its row number. Say it is l' .
- Step 7': From position (l', k') scan row l' . If column j has a `1' then we are done.

Remarks

1. Primed steps represent a 'Forward' search
2. Unprimed steps represent a 'Backward' search
3. The adjacency matrix A is sufficient to determine graph 'connectivity' which includes indirect connections.
4. This algorithm will determine at least one "3-edged" indirect path between nodes i and j , if it exists.
5. Versions of this algorithm can be created in future to determine at least one "w-edged" indirect path between nodes i and j if it exists.

Future Work

- Bimodal version
- NRR full implementation:
 - Determine every connected pair (i,j) (direct or indirect)
 - Delete all edges
 - Randomly assign routes for indirectly connected pairs

Allied Work

1. Capacity analysis
 - a. Suppose 1s are replaced by link capacities. Can we use this algorithm to compute max throughput between a pair (i,j) ?
 - b. Compare with max-flow/min-cut theorem
2. Performance analysis
 - a. Instantiate a random graph
 - b. Serve it as input to NRR
 - c. See time taken to perform NRR
 - d. Can random matrix theory plus Lovasz's paper on 'Random walks on graphs' be used to get an analytical result on speed and performance?